

2.5D-FABRICS FOR DELAMINATION RESISTANT COMPOSITE LAMINATES

I. VERPOEST, M. WEVERS, P. DE MEESTER

Departement Metaalkunde en Toegepaste Materiaalkunde,
Katholieke Universiteit Leuven, de Croylaan 2, 3030 Leuven (Belgium)

ABSTRACT

The interlaminar strength of composite laminates is very often the weak link in composite structures. A novel solution is presented, based on a new type of fabric. A three-dimensional fabric is woven in one step; pile threads connect the top and bottom twodimensional fabric. By cutting the piles, a two-and-a-half dimensional fabric can be made. It is shown that laminates, made out of these 2.5D-fabrics, show better peel strength and interlaminar fracture toughness. These properties are controlled by the pile density in the resin rich interlaminar layer.

Keywords: composite materials, fabrics, fracture toughness

INTRODUCTION

In aeronautical and astronautical applications, composite materials are mainly used for their high specific **in-plane** strength and stiffness. To minimize the mass of a structure, simply loaded in tension, the specific stiffness and strength, defined as the stiffness resp. strength divided by the density, must be maximised. Carbon fibre reinforced polymer (CFRP) laminates perform in that respect three to five times better than aluminum plates.

However, in many practical situations, **out-of-plane** loads are acting on the composite laminate, and hence can cause failure. As composite structures are often rather thin plates, impact loads perpendicular to the plate can cause important out-of plane deformations. Around bolted joints, adhesive joints and other discontinuities like laminate edges or internal ply terminations, out-of-plane stresses can easily build up. Two kinds of **interlaminar stresses** can occur: they can be either normal (mainly tensile) or shear stresses. Both can lead to delaminations, which will further weaken the laminate, and make it prone to local buckling during compression loading.

The **interlaminar strength** is the **weak link** for all composite laminates, because it totally relies on the matrix properties and on the fibre-matrix interface strength. A quick view on any mechanical properties data sheet for unidirectional composites clearly shows that the transverse tensile and the shear strength, which are matrix and interface dominated properties, are at least 10 times lower than the longitudinal tensile strength. Similar ratios can be found for the interlaminar strength compared to the longitudinal strength of unidirectional composites.

In the past, different remedies to cope with this interlaminar weakness have been tried out. Either, the **matrix** has been changed, by plasticizing epoxy resins or by using thermoplastics. Or, complicated three-dimensional structures were **woven or stitched**. Neither of these solutions is straightforward: changing the matrix introduced important new problems, like the reduced hygro-thermal properties of some toughened resins, or the high processing temperatures and hence high residual stresses of the thermoplastics. Stitching adds to the normal lamination process at least one additional production step. With three dimensional weaving, a completely different production technology is required [1,2].

So, it would be an elegant solution if the interlaminar properties of composites could be improved without changing neither the matrix nor the normal manufacturing procedure for laminates.

In this paper, a novel solution will be presented for this problem. This solution is the result of a close cooperation between a weaving company, looking for new application fields for their high technology weaving techniques, and some researchers of the Composite Materials Group K.U.Leuven. This paper reports on the exploratory studies which have been carried out during the past two years.

MANUFACTURING 2,5- AND 3D-FABRICS

The 3D-fabrics consist of two twodimensional fabrics, which are linked to each other by pile threads. The major difference with stitched composites is that these 3D-fabrics are woven in one step (fig 1): the weft threads (or "rovings") for the upper and lower fabric (or "backing") are brought separately into the weaving loom; the pile threads are connected to the warp threads, and so to the whole backing. The pile density can be changed by altering either the warp density or the "connection frequency" with the warp threads. Moreover, the pile height can vary continuously between 4 and 25 mm. The longitudinal stiffness of the fabric uniquely depends on the density and material of the weft threads.

Figure 1: weaving scheme for 2,5D- and 3D-fabrics (longitudinal cross section)

To make 2,5D-fabrics, the 3D-fabric is simply cut into an upper and a lower part, immediately after leaving the loom. -The name 2,5D-fabrics is chosen, because after cutting the pile threads only point out into half of the third dimension; one could also call it a "hairy" fabric ! -

For this exploratory research project, basically two types of 2,5D fabrics have been manufactured . - Their weaving patterns, and the materials used, are described in Table 1.- The top and bottom backings are woven with 2x68 tex E-glass rovings in weft and warp; the pile is aramid (Twaron HM from AKZO Co.) . For the 2,5D-fabrics the pile height as well as the pile density have been varied. The width of the fabrics varies between 45 and 65 mm.

TABLE 1. FABRIC DESCRIPTION

FABRIC CODE	WARP+WEFT MATERIAL	PILE MATERIAL	PILE LENGTH (mm)	PILE DENSITY (cm ⁻²)
2.5D-5	E-glass 2*68 tex	Aramid HM 1260 dtex	5	5
2.5D-6	E-glass 2*68 tex	Aramid HM 1260 dtex	5	6
2.5D-7	E-glass 2*68 tex	Aramid HM 1260 dtex	2,5	5
2.5D-8	E-glass 2*68 tex	Aramid HM 1260 dtex	2,5	6

MANUFACTURING LAMINATES

The 2,5D-fabrics are impregnated with an epoxy resin (Shell Epikote 816 + Epicure DX161, mixing ratio 100/50). To ensure good impregnation and to control the fibre-resin volume fraction, the wetted fabrics are squeezed through a set of rolls with controlled gap. Consecutively, several fabrics are stacked, and the laminate is cured using normal manufacturing procedures: in a hot press (in between two teflon foils) at 120° C for 60 minutes under a pressure of 5 bar.

Two types of specimens were made.

Figure 2: peel test specimen specimen

Figure 3: Mode I - fracture toughness test

First, to carry out the peel tests, laminates with only two plies were needed (fig.2). The specimens are 150 mm long; at one side, a teflon foil is inserted, so that the specimen can be opened easily for clamping into the tensile test machine.

Second, for the G_{Ic} fracture toughness tests, six plies were cured together with and in between two crossply glass-epoxy laminates with similar stiffness (Scotchply 1002, thickness 2.24 mm) (fig.3). The aim of this stacking sequence is to increase the specimen stiffness by increasing the thickness; but to save 2.5D-fabric material, Scotchply (3M Co.) was used. Again, a teflon foil is inserted to initiate the interlaminar crack.

For each test series, three specimen types were made, in which the stacking orientation of the pile fibres was changed (fig.4): face-to-face, back-to-back and face-to-back.

Figure 4: Three stacking orientations for the 2,5D-fabrics

PEEL TESTS

In order to get a first idea of the potential improvement of the delamination resistance, simple peel tests have been carried out. The two plies, separated at the end of the specimen by the teflon foil, are clamped into the tensile testing machine (automated Instron 6025). At a constant crosshead speed (1 mm/min) the plies of the laminate are simply teared apart. During postprocessing of the data, not only the maximum tearing stress (= load per unit specimen width) but also the tearing energy can be measured.

FRACTURE TOUGHNESS TESTS

Once the peel tests had proven the potential improvement of the interlaminar strength, mode I fracture toughness tests were carried out. The specimen (see fig.3) is mounted in special grips in the tensile testing machine. At a constant crosshead speed (1mm/min), the specimen is opened gradually, and the load-displacement curves are stored in the computer. As specimens with different initial crack lengths (or teflon strip lengths) were used, a compliance calibration curve has been built up experimentally. Using this calibration curve, and according to the method originally proposed by Berry [3], the load-displacement curves have been transformed into R-curves (crack resistance versus crack length curves).

As the pile fibres "toughen" the interlaminar layer, the results of those mode I fracture toughness tests cannot be represented by a single number (the fracture toughness, in J/m^2). In fact, only the complete R-curve can give a correct picture of the interlaminar fracture resistance of these fabrics. A procedure has been developed to approach the scattered R-curve by a function of the form

$$y = A \cdot \{ 1 - \exp(-B \cdot a) \}$$

Using a numerical method, the coefficients A and B can be calculated [5]. In this way, the asymptotic value A equals the crack propagation fracture toughness $G_{Ic,p}$. As it has been calculated in a similar and consistent way for all specimens, $G_{Ic,p}$ can be used for comparison between the different materials and stacking sequences.

RESULTS

PEEL TESTS

Measurements on the very first 2.5D-fabrics had shown that for each pile fibre type and pile length, the peel strength of the face-to-face laminates was **two to three times higher** than of the back-to-back laminates, the face-to-back laminates having intermediate values [4].

In the actual measurements however, not only the stacking orientation, but also the **pile density** and the **pile length** have been varied. The results are shown in Table 2.

In general, the face-to-face and the face-to-back laminates give higher peel strengths than the back-to-back ones. The influence of the **pile length** is not so straightforward: shorter piles seem to result in lower peel strengths, with the exception of the high density face-to-face laminate. This suggests that a minimal fibre density inbetween the laminates is needed to effectively reinforce the interlaminar layer.

TABLE 2: PEEL STRENGTH OF 2.5D-FABRIC LAMINATES (specimen width: 50mm)

FABRIC CODE	PILE LENGTH (mm) & DENSITY (#/cm ²)	PEEL STRENGTH (in N / cm)		
		back-to-back	face-to-back	face-to-face
2,5D-5	5 / 5	12.2	37.4	34.3
2,5D-6	5 / 6	12.2	29.2	21
2,5D-7	2.5 / 5	15.5	23.1	21.1
2,5D-8	2.5 / 6	12.8	24.5	30.3

TABLE 3: FRACTURE TOUGHNESS $G_{Ic,p}$ OF 2.5D-FABRIC LAMINATES

FABRIC CODE	PILE LENGTH (mm) & DENSITY (#/cm ²)	FRACTURE TOUGHNESS $G_{Ic,p}$ (in J/m ²)		
		back-to-back	face-to-back	face-to-face
2,5D-5	5 / 5	1065	1227	960
2,5D-6	5 / 6	985	---	690
2,5D-7	2.5 / 5	780	922	1097
2,5D-8	2.5 / 6	1075	1210	---

FRACTURE TOUGHNESS TESTS

Results of the fracture toughness tests, carried out on similar laminate types as the peel tests, are presented in Table 3. For the laminates with short piles, the crack propagation fracture toughness steadily increases when one goes from back-to-back over face-to-back to face-to-face stacking sequences. In other words, as the fibre density in the interlaminar layer increases, the fracture toughness increases as well. However, this simple rule seems to be violated in the laminates with long pile fibres, where a maximum is found at the face-to-back stacking sequence.

DISCUSSION

The mode I fracture toughness tests as well as the peel tests clearly indicate that the delamination resistance of fabric composites can be improved by interweaving a pile. A logic explanation should be that the pile fibres convert the interlaminar matrix rich layer into a **short fibre reinforced layer**, which is moreover bonded to the 2D-fabric. When an interlaminar crack has to grow through this layer, not only the fibres have to be broken or pulled-out, but the crack is deviated as well. All these factors together lead to a higher energy consumption per crack growth area, and hence a higher crack propagation fracture toughness.

To quantify this explanation, a model is currently under development which takes into account the total pile fibre density in the interlaminar layer. In a simplified form, this interlaminar fibre density can be represented by a **pile density factor PDF**:

$$PDF = L * D * SF$$

where

L = pile length (mm)

D = pile density (#piles/cm²)

SF = a stacking sequence factor, which is 0 for back-to-back, 1 for face-to-back and 2 for face-to-face .

Figure 5: Peel strength as a function of the pile density factor.

Figure 6: Fracture toughness $G_{Ic,p}$ as a function of the pile density factor.

The stacking sequence factor in fact equals the number of "pile layers" which enter the interlaminar matrix rich zone, whereas L and D characterize the pile density of each individual pile layer. The formula clearly expresses the fact that the same interlaminar pile density can be reached with different combinations of L , D and SF .

Using PDF as a single variable, the peel strength of all 2.5D-fabrics in all stacking sequences can be compared (fig. 5). It is obvious that a maximum is reached at $PDF = 40$. A similar curve has been found for the fracture toughness (fig.6).

The increase of the peel strength and fracture toughness with increasing interlaminar fibre density has been explained earlier: the energy needed to drive a crack through a wood of pile fibres will be proportional to the density of the wood. If however the pile density becomes too high (which was the case in two face-to-face laminates with long fibres), the pile fibres simply form additional fibre layers, which do not interact anymore.

It must be emphasized that the improvement of the interlaminar fracture toughness, obtained in these first experiments, is a lower bound.

First, the results were compared to the back-to-back laminates, and not to pure 2D-fabrics. As also at the back of the 2.5D-fabrics traces of the aramid piles are present, the actual back-to-back results are expected to be higher than the real 2D baseline data obtained from pure glass fibre 2D-fabrics.

Second, it is well known that laminates containing glass fibre fabrics have a much higher fracture toughness than carbon fibre composites; it might hence be expected that the relative increases in fracture toughness should be even higher in carbon fibre 2.5D-fabric laminates.

CONCLUSIONS

A new solution for an old composites problem has been presented: using 2,5D-fabrics, the delamination resistance of composite laminates can be drastically improved, without changing the resin or the usual laminating and curing procedure.

More research is needed to further prove the other expected advantages of this new material: high impact resistance, high open hole and bolted joint strength.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The staff members of the Schlegel Co., Mr. Demarest, Mr. Boey and Mr. Declercq, are kindly acknowledged for their cooperation, and for providing the fabrics. Most of the experimental work was carried out by students during their engineering thesis; we

thank Yves Bonte, Eric Buelens and Guy Dept for their essential contribution.

REFERENCES

1. P.S. Bruno, D.O. Keith, A.A. Vicario, " Automatically woven three-directional composite structures", SAMPE Quarterly, vol.17 (4), july 1986, pp. 10-17
2. J.C. Bittence, "Strengthening composites in three dimensions", Advanced Materials and Processes, vol.1, sept.1985, pp.46-50
3. F.X. de Charentenay, M.L.Benzeggagh, P.Davies, " Fracture mechanics applied to the delamination of composite materials", in 'Damage development and failure processes in composite materials', ed. I.Verpoest and M.Wevers, K.U.Leuven, 1987, pp.122-135
4. I.Verpoest et.al., 2.5D- and 3D-fabrics for delamination resistant composite structures, in: "New Generation Materials and Processes", Proc. European SAMPE-conference 1988, Milano, ed. F.Saporiti et.al., p.13-21
5. E.Buelens, G.Dept, Optimisation of the interlaminar fracture toughness of 2.5-D composites, Engineering Thesis, K.U.Leuven (Belgium), 1988 (*in Dutch*)